

Blacked Out Spaces: A Psychodynamic Analysis of *The God of Small Things*

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Abstract

This paper aims to present psychoanalysis of Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things* (1997) by applying Sigmund Freud's theory of consciousness, and his ideas of the Id, Ego, and the Superego. The paper expounds on the Freudian concept of the Oedipal complex, and the penis envy by using instances from the novel. The research employs descriptive, narrative, and thematic methods of literary analysis.

The psychoanalysis of *The God of Small Things* attempts to present the impact of absent parental figures on the mental state of the characters. The paper also expounds on the psychosexual stages of development as have been understood by Freud to present a detailed understanding of the actions and behaviours that the characters indulge in. The unconscious has also been explored through the analysis of the dreams experienced by different characters in the novel. At the same time, there is an attempt to understand the impact of small, seemingly inconsequential instances in shaping larger discourses. Using Roy's novel, this article aims to unpack the tussle between the Freudian concepts of the Id, Ego, and Superego and their role in a society that is replete with social prejudices around class, caste, and the accepted norms of chastity.

Keywords

Oedipal Complex, Psychoanalysis, Misplaced Emotions, Repressed Feelings, Discrimination

Introduction

Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things* (1997) is a complex narrative that explores trauma and its impact on the human psyche. It does so through the central characters of Ammu and her dizygotic twins, Rahel and Estha, and the experiences they go through in their childhood which directs their future course of action. The novel, at the same time, reveals the bare truth of the caste dynamics prevalent in contemporary Indian society. It is the transgression of these harrowing and stringent societal norms that results in the displacement of emotions of most of the characters.

It is the impact of the traumatic instances that makes the novel an interesting site for psychological inspection. Sigmund Freud, an Austrian psychologist, developed the concept of the unconscious thoroughly.

Freud believed "we are not completely rational creatures who act only on the basis of logic and intelligence, but instead are vulnerable to emotional and other kinds of non-rational or irrational appeals" (Berger 77). Therefore, this paper will analyse *The God of Small Things* through a Freudian lens. It is through the interaction between the conscious and the unconscious that human actions are governed. Freud divides the human psyche into Id, Ego, and Superego. Id, which springs from the unconscious, provokes the mind to indulge in "need-satisfying, tension-reducing activities, which are experienced as pleasure" (Lapsley and Stey 5). The Ego develops from the Id and acts as a mediator between the Id and the Superego wherein the Superego plays the role of the censor or judge for the activities the mind indulges in. However, the Superego is not an ethical agency but one that strives for perfection and can induce feelings like guilt. The Superego and the Ego are modelled according to the social environment the child has been in, which is why the actions of the characters in *The God of Small Things* are a result of the workings of their Id, Ego, and Superego.

Objective of study

This paper aims to present psychoanalysis of Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things* (1997) by applying Sigmund Freud's theory of consciousness, and his ideas of the Id, Ego, and the Superego.

Review of Literature

The God of Small Things (1997) by Arundhati Roy attracted significant scholarly attention and critical engagement. Prolific academic exploration of this multifaceted narrative has been done previously from several lenses, including those of postcolonialism, feminism, caste literature, and politics. However, despite its thorough engagement with such criticism, the novel has received comparatively little attention from a psychoanalytical

perspective. Sigmund Freud's trailblazing research work, such as *The Interpretation of Dreams* (1900) and *Beyond the Pleasure Principle* (1920), offers critical insights into the novel's representation of unconscious, familial dysfunctionality, and psychological repercussions of societal taboos. This paper aims to bridge this gap by analyzing and investigating Roy's narrative through the lens of Freudian psychoanalysis, focusing on repression, childhood trauma, and the unconscious.

Main Text**Exploring Conflicts of the Consciousness**

Mirroring the human consciousness, the narrative goes back and forth in time to reveal the story of the twins and their traumatic childhood. Freud believed that the ego employs certain techniques to "control instincts and ward off anxieties" (Berger 89). These techniques are known as defence mechanisms. The most common defence mechanism used by the conscious human mind is that of repression and suppression. Repression is a defence mechanism through which human beings tend to block their unpleasant memories, troublesome emotions, and irresistible impulses. It operates at the level of the conscious mind. Emotions like pain, suffering, and guilt are often repressed because they are deemed unacceptable many times.

This Freudian understanding of repression is evident in the characters of *The God of Small Things*. Estha, who was sexually violated by the Orangedrink Lemondrink Man, was left completely bewildered. As a child, he could not understand his awkward experience but did not know what should be his course of action. He did not know whether he would have many takers if he expressed himself boldly or if it was acceptable as per the social norms and how people would perceive him afterwards. He was a victim but as is the case with most of the victims of sexual assault, part of the blame also falls on the victim themselves. Therefore, the stigma and the lack of awareness around such an issue causes Estha to choose silence over any other course of action. This silencing of the trauma can be termed as the primary repression.

At the same time, he also tries to suppress his memories. Suppression, as understood by Freud, happens when individuals make conscious choices to avoid having certain kinds of experiences. Estha's attempt to build a hideaway at the History House was an attempt to suppress his past. He voluntarily tries to keep a backup ready to make an escape in case the situation moves out of hand. He feared that the Orangedrink Lemondrink Man would show up at Ayemenem. At a mental level, he wishes to escape the feelings causing him discomfort. This is what suppression does, it allows an individual to put uncomfortable feelings out of the mind voluntarily but they can also remember them at will.

Again, when he was sitting at the police station with Rahel, he was exposed to the trauma and was in a vulnerable state of mind. Estha is made to lie to the policeman and it is that incident that acts as a trigger forcing him to relive the traumatic experience of his childhood. This overwhelmed his Ego. Freud describes Ego "as the actual state of anxiety". Roy points it out using the lines, "silence slipped in like a bolt" (Roy 320). The twins' separation, after having experienced the death of Sophie Mol and the violence inflicted upon Velutha, impacts their psyche so strongly that Estha quits his education after school and stops communicating while Rahel becomes empty within.

Baby Kochamma tries to satisfy her hurt Ego by exacting revenge through blame. Her Ego was hurt because she was painted in a bad light in society because of remaining unmarried her entire life, while Ammu lived with confidence, unashamed of her status of being a divorcee. Having said that, Ammu's confidence could also be a pretence for inherently she too grapples with the constrictions of patriarchy. There is a clear interplay of how one character's actions affected the others relating to how the small matters accumulate and lead to huge psychological pressure. Later in the novel, it can also be seen how there is a conscious attempt to keep Sophie Mol's memory alive in the Ipe household. Her memory is a part of the dreadful past of the twins which they have tried to suppress. This suppression led to their long-term silence.

The Interplay of Dreams and Desires

Certain memories when suppressed find a way to re-enter the consciousness of the individual. Dreams provide one such entryway to the memories that the individual tries to get rid of but the subconscious does not allow for such a dismissal. Sigmund Freud in his work, *The Interpretation of Dreams*, states that dreams also play a significant role in providing an insight into the psyche of the people. Peter Barry explains what Freud conceived of dreams, he believes "that a dream is an escape-hatch or safety valve through which repressed desires, fears, or memories seek an outlet into the conscious mind" (Barry 101). In this light, analysis of the dreams that the characters in the novel experience presents a

better understanding of their unconscious thoughts. Ammu's repressed sexual attraction towards Velutha, therefore, gets manifested through her dream of the one-armed man:

Who was he, the one-armed man? Who could he have been? The God of loss? The God of Small Things? The God of Goose Bumps and Sudden Smiles? Of Sourmetal Smells – the steel bus –rails and the smell of the bus conductor's hand from holding them? (Roy 217)

The one-armed man is clearly Velutha, he is 'The God of Small Things'. Pramod K. Nayar talked about the dependence of the household on Velutha for though he is liminal owing to his caste, "the house can't function without him: to repair a pump, entertain the children, and eventually as Ammu's lover Velutha also floats between the two worlds: rich and poor, "untouchable" and "touchable"" (Nayar 237). Freud also mentions in his book, *Beyond the Pleasure Principle*, that the mind replays the traumatic incident that it experienced previously. This explains Rahel dreaming of "A fat man, faceless, killing beside a woman's corpse. Hacking its hair off. Breaking every bone of its body" (Roy 225). This fat man is a representation of Chacko's words that he had said to Ammu after her sexual union with Velutha had come to his knowledge.

This goes to show that the human personality is the result of multiple factors operating in a very complex framework. Freud believed that an imbalance between these elements would lead to a maladaptive personality. An individual who may act under the influence of the Id would have no concern whatsoever for its approval by the society or would be influenced by the Superego which may lead to repressing the Id if the action connected to it is against the social norms. In order to understand the workings of the Id, Ego, and Superego, it is impertinent to look at the socio-political conditions of the individuals under analysis.

Politics Casting a Shadow on the Psyche

The society that Roy sets her novel in is that of Ayemenem, a microcosm of the politics in Kerala. Since independence, Kerala has been under the influence of Marxism and Communism. Both these systems are based on the belief system of equality among individuals. However, the kind of Marxism and Communism that Roy presents is that of a perverted kind. There is a constant tussle in the minds of the people about practices like the caste system and categorising individuals as 'Touchables' and 'Untouchables'. The principles of equality that these Western ideals preach add to the confusion. The opportunistic forces of oppression in the novel of religion, caste, class, and gender are clearly visible. The misuse of force and power in politics is common and this directly affects the society through its percolating effect on it.

Despite the awareness about the principles of equality at the ideological level, the people of Ayemenem fail to incorporate the same in their actions. This reflects that their preconsciousness ceased to bring these practices into their consciousness. The Paradise Pickles and Preserves is symbolic of preservation of time and flawed cultural values, including the caste system. The founders of The Paradise Pickles and Preserves, Mammachi and Pappachi belonged to the upper caste "Vaishyas" while the labourers belonged to the lower caste. The centuries of suppression faced by the labourers never allowed them to raise their voice against the working conditions or the illegal production of 'banana jam' in the factory. It neither qualified as jam or jelly as per the Food Products Organisation specifications. The "difficulty that their family had with classification" (Roy 31) reverberates in their decision to continue with the illegal production of banana jam. It also seems to hint at the family's bent towards capitalism and profit making. This appears to blur the consciousness of Mammachi and Pappachi and their actions appear to be guided by their Id which operates at the pleasure principle. In this case, the monetary gratification allows them to break the rules. It also showcases double standards and hypocritical realities. Madhumita Das points out that "principles and ideals are used as a mask" to conceal the exploitative nature of society, misplaced loyalties and orthodox mentality along with refusal to change.

Later on, when Chacko inherited the factory at that time too, the relation and the attitude of the labourers towards the factory did not change. Their superego restraints them to go against the grain and question the socially prescribed norms. Social mobility to resist is further cut down due to their poverty-stricken living conditions "these social disabilities greatly reinforce purely economic inequality" (Maddison 130). Furthermore, the preference of choosing the male child over the female as the heir to the property corroborates with Freud's theory of superiority of men over women. As per Freud, women were a "dark continent". Freud considered women to be inferior to men. He reduced women's life to their

reproductive functions. According to Robin D. John, Roy mocks patriarchal oppression by deploying Social Realism. Social Realism emerged as a response to idealistic ways of living and amplified ego invigorated by Romanticism. Robin D. John further points out that "the most obvious motif of the novel is the inseparable role of sex in human life." Society is an incongruous fusion of power, caste and class dynamics. It lays bare before us a contrast of opinions and interests. *The God of Small Things* presents to the readers a realistic portrait of issues related to gender politics in India which is present even today. During Roy's time women's literary works were not that well acknowledged as their compared male counterparts. Females faced major obstacles to make a mark for themselves. The novel is also regarded by some scholars as semi-autobiographical. The novel is set in 1969, a time during which the looming presence of colonial influences were still felt. Devi Prasad Siwakoti describes *The God of Small Things* as an attempt to "subvert and disruption of the patriarchal normativity which is quite dominant in the novel." Along with the search for national identity, Roy brings to light the questions related to the feminine identity. In an interview with David Barsamian in April 2001, Arundhati Roy remarks:

Women from Kerala work throughout India and the world earning money to send back home. And yet they'll pay a dowry to get married, and they'll have the most bizarrely subservient relationships with their husbands. I grew up in a little village in Kerala. It was a nightmare for me. All I wanted to do was to escape, to get out, to never have to marry somebody there... I sometimes think I was perhaps the only girl in India whose mother said, "Whatever you do, don't get married."

This clearly shows the subservient nature of the status of women in society and how their status was frozen by the dominant sex. At the same time, the stringent caste system was, and still is, of pre-eminent importance in society. The caste system in Kerala is followed not only by the Hindus but also by the Syrian Christians which shows the way in which the notions of caste interpellate into the minds of the patriarchal society that it blurs the religious boundaries but still manages to hold significance. It is in this context that Roy, through the love affair of Ammu and Velutha, captures the transgression of the 'Love Laws' laid down by society "who should be loved, and how much" (Roy 33).

Ammu, a divorced mother of two, experiences an attraction towards Velutha, a Paravan, an 'untouchable'. There used to be a time when people from the Paravan caste were forced to sweep their footprints simply because "Brahmins or Syrian Christians would not defile themselves by accidentally stepping into a Paravan's footprint" (Roy 74). Clearly, their union transgressed the moral codes of the society for "they had made the unthinkable thinkable" (Roy 256). It is in their union that one can find the overpowering of the Id. The conflict between the Id and the Superego can be understood through Velutha's internal dialogue that the narrator lays down: "He tried to hate her (Ammu)... He couldn't" (Roy 214). Since the Superego is modelled on the social environment, knowing that Ammu is from an 'upper caste' Velutha's Superego tries to induce the feeling of hatred against her by invoking the oppression that has been inflicted upon their community by the caste to which Ammu belongs. However, the Id gains supremacy, for Velutha follows his desires. After the commission of the sexual act, Velutha's Superego reprimands him for "the terror seeped back into him" (Roy 337) but yet again the Id takes supremacy because he knew he would indulge in the act again.

The same is true of Ammu, whom society denies any form of indulgence in her sexuality. However, Ammu embraces her sexuality as she inspects her own body. "She wanted her body back. It was hers" (Roy 222). As Ammu examines her body, she tries to get hold of her sexuality which she thought had become socially redundant owing to her position as a divorcee. This act of indulging in her sexuality is an expression of the Id taking over. However, a Freudian analysis makes Ammu's position more complex for Freud associated women's sexuality with "feelings of narcissism, masochism, and passivity" (Barry 105). Freud coupled this idea with the notion that they suffer from an inferiority complex understood as the 'penis envy'. Sarah Kofman argues that Freud considered women narcissistic and that a woman's beauty and charms were compensation for "natural sexual inferiority". Viewed in this light, Ammu's defying of the social norms by being intimate with Velutha is a result of the 'penis envy' that Freud talks about.

Women's sexuality has been considered as 'madness' in Ammu's world. This madness seems to be generational as the readers are told the story of Pathil Ammai, who took off her clothes and ran "naked along the river, singing to the fish" (Roy 223). Such acts can be understood as a counteractive force to the repressed sexuality in women. Ammu's position as a divorced woman had denied

her independence and liberty. Therefore, her relationship outside the accepted boundaries is a reflection of rebellion against the denial of her own sexuality, against the socially constructed 'Love Laws'. As opposed to Ammu, Chacko indulged in his sexual desires even after his divorce, and being the male child also inherited the factory. It also reflects Ammu's limitations and subsequent desire to attain the power and control that her male counterpart, her brother, has. Her rebellion, in this sense, springs from her desire to be masculine.

This vying for power and control of the female body was and is considered to be the result of their "penis envy". However, Luce Irigaray in *The Sex Which is Not One* (1977) refutes this Freudian understanding of female sexuality and opines that women do not have one sex, but multiple sex organs all over their body including the two lips meant for their pleasure. Further, Irigaray states that Freud's approaches have "always been theorised within masculine parameters" (23). This by default relegates women to an inferior position in society. In this regard, Ammu's actions would be seen as a response to the multiple oppressive mechanisms that are at work. Her rebellion becomes much more nuanced rather than being just an extension of Freudian 'penis envy'. Apart from being a rebellion, Ammu's illicit affair is also a medium of escape from the layers of trauma that affect her as a divorced mother of two.

Trauma as an Inheritance

The novel explores the idea of trauma being passed on from one generation to the other. Psychological distress witnessed as a child is like a skeleton in the cupboard which possesses the potential influence and damage to an individual as an adult. The memory of their mother being beaten up by their father imprinted itself in the young minds of the siblings, Ammu and Chacko. Their marital relationship was a strained and tenuous one. The unconscious mind influences people's everyday life by affecting their decision-making skills. It acts as a 'cauldron' or repertoire of all those disturbing memories that one keeps locked up inside themselves. The experience of dysfunctional family architecture as children was replicated in the relationships they entered into as adults. The unconscious which was perhaps being reconciled by the preconscious ultimately came to the conscious when both Ammu and Chacko realised their incompatibility with their respective partners and opted for divorce. Perhaps both of them tried their best to avoid and escape the experience of marital discord by opting for inter-communal and inter-religious 'love' marriages respectively. Yet Ammu married an alcoholic who mentally tortured her. He tried to force Ammu to sleep with his boss for the sake of his job. Chacko married a British woman, Margaret whom he met at a café during his time at Oxford where she worked as a waitress. However, how much of a conscious choice they made in these so-called love marriages is a question mark. K.J. Sibi also points out how the narrative technique uses trauma as an instrument to "make the readers experience the same once again". Rahel is made to return to Ayemenem from the US at the age of thirty-one. It is the same age at which Ammu also came back with the twins.

In the same sense, Rahel and Estha too transgress the 'Love Laws' that Ammu had done. The twins are never seen as separate individuals but always as a whole since "isolated things don't mean anything" (Roy 225). It is for this reason that the twins experience a void too large to be filled when separated. Both had devised their own mechanisms to defend themselves from the trauma and the tragic loss of Sophie Mol, Velutha, and Ammu that they had experienced. While Estha gave up his speech, Rahel became emotionally numb. Until the 'terror', Ammu had been asserting herself in the roles of both mother and father but she doesn't seem to succeed, for the twins search for alternative father figures in Chacko and Velutha. However, both alternatives cannot fill the void. The feeling of loneliness and being devoid of any security creeps up in the twins due to the absence of the paternal figure which is coupled with the mother's anguished cry, "I should have dumped you in an orphanage the day you were born! You're the millstones around my neck" (Roy 253). This trigger along with Estha's need to escape from the trauma of the Orangedrink Lemondrink Man becomes the eventual cause of the "terror".

Their union then is the coming together of "Quietness and Emptiness" (Roy 327). It is understood to be an act of forming a trauma bond. However, the act is not just a result of the search for an identity that had been lost due to the trauma but also an example of what Freud defines as the Oedipus complex. Freud mentions in his work, *On Narcissism: an Introduction*, that the choice of partner during marriage is influenced by one's childhood experiences. He claims that women are more likely than men to opt for a narcissistic partner. On the other hand, men would lean more towards the anaclitic type where they would seek to find a

mother in their potential female partner. At the level of one's Ego, the narcissistic choice gives rise to romantic feelings and love. The partner tends to attribute those qualities to the romantic partner that they themselves wish to possess.

In fact, the incestuous desires of Estha do not emerge from the need for oneness but rather from the need to be with his mother again. His identification of Rahel with Ammu has been done before their sexual union, for he refers to Rahel's mouth as their "beautiful mother's mouth, Estha thought. Ammu's mouth" (Roy 300). Estha's fixation on his mother can be understood as a desire to overcome the loss of Ammu. At the same time, the twins held themselves completely culpable for Ammu's death, and to shield himself from this guilt that the Superego has produced, Estha seeks a "return to origin and wholeness through the imaging of Rahel as the mother" (Eldred 75).

Their incest is understood to be parallel to the union of Ammu and Velutha, both being transgressions of the 'Love Laws' laid down by the society. However, while Ammu's sexual union with Velutha is a positive act of rebellion, the twins' sexual union does not achieve the same result. The fact that the twins are ultimately separate identities makes the union futile. Roy, despite what the twins perceive, has carefully articulated the differences that exist between the twins. The two do not resemble each other and Baby Kochamma, having perceived the difference of nature chooses Estha to frame Velutha for he is the "more farsighted. The more responsible" (Roy 319).

At the same time, while their union seemed to be a rebellion against the societal agents that form 'Love Laws', of "Freudian morality that would separate and dominate the twins" (Eldred 71) it is, in fact, this very act of interdependence that makes the twins turn back to the family's history for a similar bond has been formed between Chacko and Mammachi. Chacko was Mammachi's "man, her only love" (Roy 168). This desire is so strong that Mammachi hated Margaret Kochamma for being his wife, while Chacko always needed and demanded Mammachi's adoration. This pattern of incestuous relationships is therefore only re-enacted and repeated by the twins. In this sense, the union is indeed a representation of intergenerational trauma. Therefore, there is an intersection of history and family at play in the novel. Rahel and Estha's roles are merely performative as they become puppets at the hands of familial history.

For Rahel, the union is an act of filling the void she experiences. As a young girl, Rahel had been neglected and compared to her cousin, Sophie Mol. Sophie Mol had a racial advantage over Rahel since her mother was a Britisher which made Sophie a half-Indian, half-English hybrid of cultures. Her white skin was seen as an embodiment of so-called moral 'piousness'. In her, the elders of the Ipe family saw the refinement of their own 'genes' since she had Pappachi's nose, blue eyes, and a light complexion. Clearly, the perception of superiority of the ruling class can be seen in the preconscious minds of the family members and in general, the people at Ayemenem. Frantz Fanon in *Black Skin White Masks* points out that because of colonisation, the belief of the White Man's racial superiority deeply embedded itself in the minds of the colonised people. They began to perceive themselves as victimised and gradually became alienated from their own sense of self and identity. This preconscious perception immediately came to the forefront of the conscious when they saw Sophie Mol. By her unfair comparison with Rahel which was based on their assumptions and expectations about Sophie Mol as a child, she is considered to be superior to Rahel. At this juncture, Rahel experiences an inferiority complex and develops a sense of nervousness as a child.

She found solace only in the company of her twin. Therefore, after separation from Estha, she becomes indifferent to the world around her, she isolates herself for she feels incomplete without her twin. Jacques Lacan, a French psychoanalyst, also called the French Freud, drew on Freud's concept of 'desire' that can be obtained when it is expressed and demanded. However, Lacan differentiates 'desire' from need and demand. When the need gets appeased or fulfilled, the demand for love still stays unfulfilled. Therefore, what remains behind is called desire. Lacan believes "desire begins to take shape in the margin in which demand becomes separated from need" (Lacan 222). In this sense, desire is insatiable.

In this light, Rahel expresses the desire and "creates the need by provoking Esthappen." (Saravanan 179). No one could understand Estha like she did. Her love for Estha is unique and one that cannot be labelled for when she meets Estha after twenty-three years she "watched Estha with the curiosity of a mother watching her wet child. A sister, a brother. A woman a man. A twin, a twin." (Roy 93). It is this love that gets translated into the desire that Rahel, according to Lacanian principle, formulates, creates, names, and brings forth. It is the result of

this desire that makes Rahel and Estha look for alternative father figures. The failure of this leads to the twins desiring each other. While Estha's desire has been understood as the Oedipus Complex, Rahel's desire can be seen as the female equivalent of it. Freud extensively talks about the male child and his sexual desires but doesn't include in his theories the female child's predicament. Therefore, Freud's successor, Carl Jung adds to this discussion by introducing the concept of Electra Complex. It is the fixation of the girl child that leads to her developing an attraction towards her father. In Rahel's case, the absence of this father figure and the eventual absence of the mother ends up transferring her desire towards her brother, her twin, Estha.

The desire for an alternate father figure can also be read as the twins' attempt to incorporate themselves into the socially constructed norm of the family. However, in their attempts to fill the void caused by the displacement of parental figures, they transgress the bounds of socially accepted relationships. Such a transgression is Roy's attempt at critiquing the issues of socially constructed notions of family. Even in contemporary society, there exists a taboo around families that have only one parent. Here too, the politics of gender play a crucial role. While a single father is often looked at with sympathy and is praised for raising the child/children all by himself, a single mother is usually subjected to criticism and seen as an outcast. Such households are often termed as "broken" and are the victims of the process of othering. In such a society, the position of Rahel and Estha is as it is vulnerable and susceptible to psychological influences.

However, Rahel's desire is more complex than this. Her lack of interest in academics, social aloofness, and eventually failed marriage are all symptoms of her being fixated on what Freud understood to be the Latency stage of psychosexual development. Freud believed that there are five basic stages of development in every individual. These stages are the Oral stage, Anal stage, Phallic Stage, Latency period, and Genital stage. The fixation in the Latency stage occurs due to the child's struggle to form social bonds and develop social skills leading to isolation and an identity crisis. Due to the traumatic events that Rahel experiences in her Latency period, she remains fixated on that stage which explains the failure of her marriage with Larry and the reason for her feeling unloved and unsatisfied. Considering this Freudian understanding, the desire Rahel has for Estha is then out of a search for her own identity and completeness.

Conclusion

Therefore, it is through the analysis of the characters, and a psychoanalytic reading of the experiences they go through, that it can be observed that the repressed desires and feelings are the cause of their aberrant and unorthodox behaviours. The application of Freud's psychosexual analysis reveals Rahel's fixation and explains not only her aloofness, and sexual dissatisfaction with her partner but also the need to be one with Estha. Estha's union with Rahel is a clear reflection of his being fixated on his mother, and is hence, a victim of the Oedipal complex. *The God of Small Things*, in this sense, explores the impact that traumatic experiences have on the psyche of children and thereby shapes their outlook and perceptions as adults.

The dreams that Ammu and Rahel experience imply a Freudian theory since the dreams manifest the deep-seated desires that the unconscious of the characters had been trying to repress. The constant tussle between the Id, Ego, and Superego is unpacked through a thorough analysis of the novel, revealing how the social prejudices around class, caste, and accepted norms of chastity craft an individual's mental framework. The re-enactment and indulgence in bonds that are outside the accepted social norms show a pattern of inter-generational trauma that is explored through the twins' incestuous act and Ammu's sexual union with an 'untouchable'. At the same time, Ammu's rebellion against the patriarchal forces and indulgence in her sexuality is a reflection of her 'penis envy' that Roy expounds upon. A Freudian analysis of *The God of Small Things*, therefore, cuts right through the complex psyche on which humans function, reiterating the idea that it is the small things that affect the bigger things as Roy mentions, "only the Small Things are ever said. Big Things lurk unsaid inside" (Roy 142).

The psychoanalytical reading of the text also brings to the fore the question of the significance of the social fabric. The norms that exist in society are by no means natural but are constructed through historical processes and cultural dominance. In today's capitalistic world, where the value of most relationships is gauged based on materialistic endeavours, where desire, and not love, is the driving factor for most actions, an understanding of the underlying psychological processes becomes impertinent. It is the desire for completeness, for constructing a family that is deemed as the norm, and for breaking away from the restrictions of society that leads to the psychological upheaval of the twins. The interplay of sexuality, historical and cultural context, familial bonds, and incidents in

childhood all become major factors in shaping the psyche of an individual. Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things* is, therefore, a quintessential exploration of the psychodynamics of contemporary society.

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Disclosure statement

The authors report that there are no competing interests to declare.